

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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ISSUES OF USING FOREIGN LOANS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TRANSPORT SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Since 1996, political tensions among Central Asian states have resulted in major disruptions in regional transportation. Uzbekistan faced serious challenges due to the closure of railway connections with Khorezm, Surkhandarya, and Karakalpakstan, along with transit fee demands in foreign currency. These restrictions critically impacted the Fergana Valley transport corridor, which serves as a vital link for 10 million residents and houses the country's only oil refinery. In response to the economic blockade, the Uzbek government undertook urgent strategic actions. Faced with a budget deficit, the country increasingly relied on external borrowing. This paper explores the causes, characteristics, and governance aspects of Uzbekistan's external debt policy in the context of developing its transportation infrastructure. Using a comparative analysis approach, the article provides an original evaluation of external debt utilization in major transport investment projects.

Key words: state, law, railroad, highway, transit, corridor, budget, internal public debt, external public debt, credit.

Annotatsiya: 1996-yildan boshlab Markaziy Osiyo davlatlari o'rtasidagi siyosiy ziddiyatlar transport tizimida jiddiy uzilishlarga olib keldi. Xususan, O'zbekiston Respublikasining boshqa hududlari bilan Xorazm, Surxondaryo va Qoraqalpog'iston temir yo'l aloqalari to'xtatilgan holatlarda valyutada tranzit to'lovi talabi joriy etildi. Farg'ona vodiysi transport yo'lagi muammosi respublika miqyosida strategik ahamiyat kasb etib, ushbu hududdagi yagona neftni qayta ishlash zavodining faoliyati ham xavf ostida qoldi. O'zbekiston hukumati ushbu muammoni hal etish uchun jiddiy tashabbuslarni boshladi. Davlat byudjeti katta tanqislik sharoitida bo'lganligi sababli, xorijiy qarzlardan keng foydalanishga zarurat tug'ildi. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda transport tizimi rivojida tashqi qarzdan foydalanishning sabablari, xususiyatlari va boshqaruv tamoyillari muallif tomonidan tahlil qilinadi. Komparativ tahlil asosida tashqi moliyaviy resurslarning roli va imkoniyatlari baholanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat, qonun, temir yo'l, avtomobil yo'li, tranzit, yo'lak, byudjet, davlat ichki qarzi, davlat tashqi qarzi, kredit.

Аннотация: С 1996 года в результате политических разногласий между странами Центральной Азии в транспортной системе региона наблюдаются серьезные сбои. Особенно остро эти проблемы проявились в Узбекистане, где были нарушены железнодорожные связи с Хорезмом, Сурхандарьей и Каракалпакстаном, а за транзит стали требовать оплату в иностранной валюте. Особую тревогу вызвала ситуация с транспортным коридором в Ферганскую долину, где проживают 10 миллионов человек и расположено единственное нефтеперерабатывающее предприятие страны. В условиях бюджетного дефицита руководство республики было вынуждено активно использовать внешние заимствования. В данной статье рассматриваются причины привлечения внешнего долга, особенности его управления и роль в развитии транспортной системы Узбекистана. Автор проводит сравнительный анализ и дает экспертную оценку использования внешнего финансирования в крупных инфраструктурных проектах.

Ключевые слова: государство, закон, железная дорога, автотрасса, транзит, коридор, бюджет, внутренний долг, внешний долг, кредит.

INTRODUCTION

The experience of international practice demonstrates that there is virtually no country in the world today that has not incurred a certain level of foreign debt from international financial institutions, major commercial banks, or through the issuance of sovereign securities. Currently, the issue of external public debt has become a global economic concern and is attracting the close attention not only of economists but also of policymakers and international institutions.

In particular, the challenges associated with managing foreign debt have intensified in light of the measures taken to mitigate the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting sharp decline in economic activity. To stimulate economic growth, revitalize investment activity, restore production levels, increase employment, raise household incomes, and support business entities, a significant number of countries including those

with advanced economies have been compelled to allocate substantial financial resources to their national economies. These efforts have been particularly focused on maintaining the liquidity and stability of the financial and banking sectors.

As a consequence, many countries, including Uzbekistan, have experienced substantial government budget deficits and a rise in public debt, leading to notable financial imbalances. In this context, the further development of both the theoretical and practical foundations of public debt management is emerging as a critical issue in ensuring sustainable economic development.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Research on the effective use of external debt in national economic development particularly in transport infrastructure has been extensively conducted by international financial institutions such as the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the Center on Budget and Policy Priorities, the Victoria State Government, the Vice Presidency of the Government of Spain, the National Association of State Budget Officers, and the Maine State Legislature.

In academic discourse, the problem of utilizing foreign debt for economic growth has been a central focus for many leading economists. John Maynard Keynes emphasized the strategic use of public borrowing to stimulate economic activity during downturns. Eaton and Gersovitz developed a theoretical framework on sovereign debt that explores default risks and creditor relations. Pegkas provided empirical insight into the relationship between public debt and economic growth using the case of Greece, showing that the effectiveness of debt depends on how it is managed and allocated. Amadeo and Tully explored the paradox of rising national deficits even in high-performing economies like the United States, raising concerns about fiscal sustainability.

From a national perspective, several Uzbek scholars have contributed to the understanding of public debt within the country's transport system. Alimov investigated banking reforms as a critical factor in promoting economic growth in emerging markets such as Uzbekistan. Sultanova and Babakhanova focused on the statistical analysis of cargo transport efficiency in the railway sector. Djumanova and her colleagues explored accounting organization and financial control mechanisms in "Uzbekistan Railways," offering valuable insights into domestic debt management and logistics optimization.

Collectively, these works provide a robust foundation for evaluating the challenges and opportunities of using foreign loans in developing Uzbekistan's transport infrastructure.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this research is grounded in the analysis of theoretical and empirical studies conducted by both foreign and Uzbek economists. The research applied a combination of methods to examine the use of foreign loans in the transport system, including scientific abstraction, logical observation, critical literature review, data grouping, comparison, and systematic economic analysis.

To substantiate the arguments, data from the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Transport, and the Central Bank were analyzed. Additionally, statistical information from the official website of the World Bank was utilized to compare trends in public borrowing and infrastructure investment.

The article's methodological framework is also supported by academic literature that examines public finance, debt sustainability, and sector-specific investment strategies. The interdisciplinary approach adopted in this study helps to comprehensively assess the implications of foreign debt usage in the transport sector, particularly regarding its long-term economic impact and management challenges.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the management of the state budget of each individual country, the issue of state external debt and its proper administration becomes critically important. The process of public debt formation and management can be defined as a set of complex economic relations that arise throughout the production cycle, as well as during the distribution, exchange, and consumption of material, financial, and intellectual resources. These relationships are formed between states and economic entities at both the domestic and international levels.

Government borrowing typically occurs under the following key circumstances:

Firstly, when there is a disequilibrium between public revenues and expenditures, resulting in a state budget deficit. In such cases, foreign borrowing is often utilized to cover the shortfall and maintain essential public services.

Secondly, foreign loans are employed to finance large-scale public investment projects, such as those related to infrastructure, energy, and transportation, which require substantial upfront capital.

Thirdly, public borrowing becomes necessary in emergency situations such as armed conflicts, natural disasters, or pandemics. In such instances, the state's internal reserves may be insufficient to meet urgent economic and humanitarian needs, thereby necessitating access to external sources of funding.

The experience of global economic practice confirms that many countries have actively used external public debt to support national economic development and to compensate for budgetary deficits through non-linear and alternative mechanisms. Notably, during the period of the COVID-19 pandemic and in its aftermath, numerous states resorted to significant foreign borrowing to ensure the liquidity of their financial and banking sectors, support employment, and maintain the functioning of key infrastructure systems.

As illustrated in Figure 1 (see below), the trends in global sovereign debt accumulation, particularly from 2010–2023, reflect the increasing reliance of both developing and developed economies on external sources of capital. In Uzbekistan's case, external borrowing during 2020–2023 expanded rapidly as the country sought to finance strategic infrastructure projects, including those in the transportation sector. This was especially relevant for initiatives aimed at restoring and modernizing national railway and highway networks, ensuring uninterrupted connectivity across key economic regions such as the Fergana Valley.

Furthermore, the effective management of external debt including loan agreements, repayment schedules, interest servicing, and risk mitigation has become a strategic priority. It is essential not only for maintaining macroeconomic stability but also for improving investor confidence and securing continued access to international capital markets.

The government's approach to debt management must therefore be carefully calibrated to balance short-term financing needs with long-term sustainability. In this context, Uzbekistan's reliance on foreign loans for transport infrastructure should be guided by comprehensive feasibility studies, transparent procurement mechanisms, and efficient public financial management practices.

Figure 1. The main factors of public borrowing¹.

It should be noted that a comparable situation is currently being observed in Uzbekistan. The challenges related to external borrowing and budget deficits are not unique to developing countries. In fact, member states of the European Union and other developed economies have also experienced significant external debt burdens and fiscal imbalances during critical phases of their development.

In particular, the Eurozone countries (currently comprising 27 EU member states) have adopted institutional constraints on public borrowing. According to the Maastricht Treaty, which has been in force since May 2, 1993, EU member countries are required to adhere to specific fiscal criteria in order to qualify for membership in the monetary union. One of the key requirements is that the ratio of government debt to gross domestic product (GDP) must not exceed 60.0 percent, or at the very least, show a stable and continuous tendency toward this threshold. This requirement is known as the Maastricht debt criterion, and it serves as a strict benchmark for ensuring fiscal discipline and macroeconomic stability among participating countries.

In international economic practice, public debt is generally classified into two main categories based on its origin: domestic debt and foreign (external) debt.

Domestic public debt refers to the liabilities incurred by the state as a result of borrowing from internal sources, including the general population, local businesses, and domestic financial institutions such as commercial banks.

External public debt, on the other hand, is the obligation of a country to foreign creditors. This includes loans obtained from other governments, multilateral financial institutions (such as the World Bank or the International Monetary Fund), and international commercial banks, including those organized under global creditor consortiums such as the London Club.

¹ The picture was prepared by the author.

In the case of Uzbekistan, the composition of public debt has increasingly shifted toward external sources particularly since 2020 as the government intensifies investment in critical infrastructure sectors, including transport and logistics. This trend aligns with global practices, where countries have turned to foreign borrowing as a countercyclical tool to stimulate economic growth, especially during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 2. The composition of public debt in international practice²

In international practice, the total external debt of a country is generally divided into two main categories: Public debt and debts guaranteed by the state (public external debt) – This includes all borrowings undertaken directly by the government or secured through sovereign guarantees. These debts are typically contracted with foreign governments, international financial institutions, or global commercial banks. In many developing economies, including Uzbekistan, this category represents the bulk of total foreign debt due to the state-led nature of infrastructure financing.

Unsecured external debt (private external debt) – This consists of borrowings by private entities and corporations that are not backed by sovereign guarantees. Such debt is incurred directly by businesses through foreign investors, financial markets, or international lenders without direct state responsibility for repayment.

Figure 3. The composition of the total debt of the state in international practice³.

In Uzbekistan, state debt and state-guaranteed debts are regulated through the annual adoption of the State Budget Law. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2025”, adopted on December 24, 2024, specific limits were established for new external borrowing for the upcoming fiscal year.

For the year 2025, the maximum volume of newly signed foreign debt agreements, on behalf of the Republic of Uzbekistan and under its sovereign guarantee, was set at 5.5 billion US dollars. Out of this amount, 3.0 billion US dollars is allocated to support the state budget, including financing its anticipated fiscal deficit. This reflects the government’s continued strategy of leveraging foreign loans not only for infrastructure and development projects but also as a mechanism to maintain budgetary stability and liquidity.

In international financial practice, unsecured external debts refer to liabilities incurred without state guarantees. These are typically contracted by private economic entities—including corporations, commercial banks, and industry stakeholders from foreign commercial lenders and international financial institutions.

² The picture was prepared by the author.

³ The picture was prepared by the author.

In Uzbekistan, private foreign debt is primarily linked to the activities of large commercial banks operating within the country, as well as enterprises in key strategic sectors such as the energy industry (notably oil and gas), the mining and metallurgical complex, and various export-oriented industries. These sectors tend to access international capital to finance modernization, technological upgrades, and raw material procurement.

The following table presents detailed data on the components of Uzbekistan's total external debt for the period from 2014–2024, distinguishing between public external debt and private (unsecured) external debt, and offering insights into trends in debt accumulation and sectoral distribution.

Table 1. Information on the components of the total foreign debt of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2014-2024 y⁴ (in us \$ billion).

№	Years	Total external debt	including			
			Foreign debt of the state	Share %	Private foreign debt	Share %
1	2014 year	9,4	3,9	41,5	5,5	58,5
2	2015 year	11,2	4,3	38,4	6,9	61,6
3	2016 year	13,0	5,7	43,8	7,3	56,2
4	2017 year	14,7	6,5	44,2	8,2	55,8
5	2018 year	15,8	7,6	48,1	8,2	51,8
6	2019 year	17,2	10,0	58,1	7,2	41,9
7	2020 year	24,6	15,9	64,6	8,7	35,4
8	2021 year	34,2	21,4	62,6	12,8	37,4
9	2022 year	39,6	23,7	59,8	15,9	40,2
10	2023 year	53,0	29,7	56,0	23,3	44,0
11	2024 year	60,2	32,5	54,0	27,7	46,0

An analysis of the data presented in the table above shows that until 2019, private external debt held a dominant share in the structure of Uzbekistan's total external debt. For instance, in 2018, the share of private external debt amounted to 51.8 percent, or US \$8.2 billion, of the total external debt.

However, since 2018, there has been a notable increase in the share of state external debt within the total foreign debt structure. For example, in 2024, state external debt accounted for 54.0 percent of the Republic's total external obligations. This shift reflects a strategic policy orientation toward state-led borrowing for national development, particularly in infrastructure and strategic sectors.

As evidenced by the data, Uzbekistan's total external debt structure is increasingly driven by public borrowing, particularly loans contracted or guaranteed by the government. As of January 1, 2025, private external debt reached US \$27.7 billion, marking an increase of 11.9 percent, or US \$4.4 billion, compared to the beginning of 2023. This growth is primarily attributed to commercial banks, the energy sector (notably oil and gas), the mining and metallurgical industries, and other corporate borrowers operating within high-capital sectors.

Historically, Uzbekistan's engagement with the global financial system began soon after its independence. The country joined the United Nations in March 1992, and became a member of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) on September 21, 1992, which functions as the UN's financial agency. Additionally, Uzbekistan joined the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank) on June 2, 1992.

The first foreign loans in Uzbekistan's history were provided by the IMF and the World Bank. It is important to note that these initial loans were not directed toward industrial expansion, but rather were allocated for the development of the education system, improvements in water supply, reconstruction of transport infrastructure, and strengthening of the financial and banking systems.

As Uzbekistan's national economy gradually recovered and began to modernize, the range of creditors expanded. The country joined the Asian Development Bank (ADB) on August 31, 1995, and received its first ADB loan to support the development of railway infrastructure and the construction of new railway lines.

One of the major infrastructure achievements made possible through foreign borrowing was the construction and launch of the Navoi–Uchkuduk–Sultan Uvaystog'–Nukus railway in 1997, financed through a US \$70 million loan from the Asian Development Bank. In 1998, another US \$40 million loan from ADB was used to modernize the Tashkent depot serving 1,520 mm broad-gauge railway cars.

Further development included the construction of new railway lines such as Toshguzar–Boysun–Kumqurgan and Angren–Pop, both financed through loans from the Chinese Development Bank. Additionally,

4 The picture was prepared by the author.

the construction of the Savay–Xonobod railway in the Fergana Valley strengthened regional connectivity and enhanced the internal mobility of goods and passengers.

As a result, Uzbekistan has achieved significant improvements in its transport and logistics systems, which now ensure reliable domestic and international transit of cargo. These strategic developments have reduced dependence on neighboring countries for key transit routes and made it possible to save several hundred million US dollars annually in international freight and passenger transportation costs.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that the Republic of Uzbekistan has made significant progress in developing its railway infrastructure through the use of external debt. Notable achievements include the construction of new railway lines and the modernization of existing networks, which have been largely financed by foreign loans from international financial institutions. These investments have played a crucial role in improving the country's domestic and international transport connectivity.

However, despite these developments, several issues remain unresolved in the field of railway transport. In particular, the implementation of strategic projects such as establishing railway connections to seaports via the Uzbekistan–Afghanistan–Pakistan and Uzbekistan–Kyrgyzstan–China corridors is actively under discussion. In our view, the main obstacle to the realization of these projects lies in the issue of financing.

This challenge is largely due to the fact that the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan is currently being implemented with a considerable deficit, which significantly limits the state's capacity to finance large-scale railway construction from domestic budgetary resources.

In our opinion, the following two strategic directions can offer a viable path toward addressing the existing financing gap:

First, it is necessary to continue attracting external debt to support the construction of new railway lines and infrastructure. This remains a critical tool for accelerating development, especially in strategically important corridors.

Second, greater emphasis should be placed on mobilizing private capital into railway development projects. Expanding public–private partnerships and reducing the burden of foreign debt obligations on the state will contribute to long-term fiscal sustainability.

Uzbekistan has already established a favorable investment climate, including a system of tax incentives, preferences, and legal guarantees to protect foreign investors. Building on this foundation, it is essential to further strengthen mechanisms that encourage domestic investors to participate in financing national infrastructure projects.

We believe that the implementation of the above proposals will enhance the role of domestic capital in public debt financing and reduce the country's dependence on foreign loans. This, in turn, will contribute to the development of a more resilient and self-sufficient national economy.

List of references used

1. International Debt Statistics 2023. International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank.
2. <https://www.cbpp.org/research/policy-basics-the-abcs-of-state-budgets>
3. <https://www.dtf.vic.gov.au/state-budget>
4. <https://www.hacienda.gob.es/en-B/Areas%20Tematicas/Presupuestos%20Generales%20del%20Estado/Paginas/Presupuestos.aspx>
5. <https://www.nasbo.org/reports-data/budget-processes-in-the-states>
6. <https://legislature.maine.gov/ofpr/total-state-budget-information/9304>
7. Amadeo K. The US debt and how it got so big. Five reasons why America is in debt. *The Balance*, 2019, March 28. Mode of access: <http://www.thebalance.com/u-s-debt-and-how-it-got-so-big-3305778>
8. Eaton J., Gersovitz M. Debt with Potential Repudiation: Theoretical and Empirical Analysis. *The Review of Economic Studies*, Vol. 48, No. 2, April 1981, pp. 298–300
9. Keynes J.M. *The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money*. Macmillan Cambridge University Press, 1936. URL: <https://www.marxists.org/reference/subject/economics/keynes/general-theory/index.htm>
10. Pegkas P. The effect of government debt and other determinants on economic growth: The Greek experience. *Economies*, 6(1), 2018
11. Tully S. America's disastrous new normal: A booming economy and soaring deficits. *The Fortune*, 2019, January 5. Mode of access: <http://fortune.com/2019/01/05/us-economy-deficit-government>
12. Alimov I.I. Prospective banking reforms are the solution for the economic growth in emerging economies like Uzbekistan. *International Scientific Journal «Theoretical & Applied Science»*, Philadelphia, USA, 21.05.2019, pp. 139–144
13. Sultanova S.M., Babakhanova N.U. Statistical model for determining the quality of cargo work JSC Uzbekistan Railways. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 2023, 402

14. Djumanova A.B., Uldasheva M.M. Improving the Organization of Accounting for Internal Production Divisions of Enterprises. E3S Web of Conferences, Vol. 401, p. 05088, EDP Sciences, 2023
15. Dzhumanova A.B., Kushakova M.N., Khodzhaeva N.A. Formation of accounting management information in the control system of enterprises of JSC Uzbekistan Railways. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 2019, Vol. 28, No. 14, pp. 32–36
16. Baxtiyarovna D.A., Usmandjanovna B.N., Amanbayevna A.R., Mirzaxmatovna Y.M. The Role of Management Accounting in the Construction of Logistics Business Processes. Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education, 2021, 12(11), pp. 693–696
17. Law No. 1011 of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2025”, adopted on December 24, 2024. Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2024
18. <http://www.cbu.uz> – Official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan
19. <http://www.mf.uz> – Official website of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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